

'HJT 2.0' PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENTS AND COST BENEFITS FOR SILICON HETEROJUNCTION CELL PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT: Silicon heterojunction technology (HJT) for mass production frequently meets reservations related to the performance and cost constraints the standard TCO on the cell front side namely indium tin oxide (ITO) constitutes. We address and mitigate these concerns with our HJT 2.0 concept in which the front electrode is made of a bi-layer of much thinner ITO that is supplemented by a silicon nitride (SiN) layer. This cell concept was developed to yield an improvement in device efficiency of typically 0.2% absolute due to increased cell current and a considerable cost saving of around 0.5ct\$/Wp with respect to cost of ownership (CoO) for the module.

Keywords: Heterojunction, TCO, ITO, SiN, bi-layer, HJT2.0, CoO, solar cell production,

1 INTRODUCTION

Silicon based HJT is gaining momentum as a large volume solar cell production technology [1,2,3], falling in step with the industries demand for technology improvements beyond the level of standard PERC, a technology that after a period of strong production expansion with cost & performance progress very successfully replaced the Al-BSF cell technology as its upgrade in recent years. This development has generally been expected and predicted for a while as is evident for example in the ITRPV road maps [4]. In fact many forecasted a sizeable market entry phase for HJT much earlier which did not materialize likely due to two developments, namely continued performance improvements of the PERC technology along with massive cost reductions beyond expectations at the time of forecasting. These developments made a timely market entry arduous for HJT even if a superior cell and module performance with a pronounced LCOE advantage and the sustained potential for even higher cell and module efficiencies in mass production was demonstrated over the years with increasingly mature data, e.g. from Meyer Burger's HJT demo line in Germany [5] or the "LabFab" of CEA-INES [6]. Along with the performance improvement and technology maturation the cost structures evolved and stayed favorable for the CoO of HJT compared to all the diffused homo-junction technologies including PERC, nevertheless it appears this was not sufficient to make cell producers deploy the technology on a larger production scale yet, though enough to engage many in serious R&D activities. Some of the reservation for a fast HJT adoption is certainly linked to the fact that contrary to the silicon homo-junction cell technologies HJT uses TCOs, typically ITO, for an efficient cell contacting, a layer material essential for thin film solar cells, however not used for and thus unknown to traditional homo-junction c-Si technologies. Aforementioned use of TCO impacts cell performance and production costs. In the following we will elude to each topic in more detail, first the performance related aspects succeeded by cost implications.

2 HJT CELL PERFORMANCE WITH RESPECT TO TRANSPARENT CONDUCTING OXIDES

While the Holy Grail with respect to performance improvement for diffused homo-junction c-Si cells is refined passivation with a Voc target towards 700mV, HJT passivation allows for typical HJT cells with VOCs

at around and possibly exceeding 740mV already since many years, in fact VOCs becoming increasingly limited by the wafer bulk quality due to excellent passivation quality provided by HJT. Thus, for HJT cells the focus with respect to performance improvement is the short circuit current density of the device Jsc. The commonly applied ITO being an excellent TCO, limits nevertheless the cell's Jsc largely due to free carrier absorption in the infrared and the blue spectral range due to free carrier absorption. This intrinsic limitation has been addressed by a number of research groups in different ways, the common one by engineering the TCO such that conductivity was preserved while reducing the carrier concentration and hence IR-absorption together with increasing carrier mobility via process development with materials like IWO, ICO, IO:H etc. [7]. Yet these higher performing TCOs will typically come with an undesired cost penalty and additional constraints in production.

At Meyer Burger Research AG (MBR) we started following a different R&D route, i.e. thinning down the front TCO and ensuring optimized antireflective (AR) properties by adding transparent non-conductive SiNx:H (SiN), the standard front side dielectric in homo-junction cells. The excellent passivation of HJT devices enables this liberty in cell design without comprising performance; by employing the emitter on the rear side, which in terms elevates constraints on the conductivity of the front TCO because the high minority carrier concentration in operation with diffusion lengths in the mm range provides sufficient lateral conductivity for efficient transport. In addition, the optical transparency of the front side passivation stack is increased while maintaining the highest passivation quality. Together with the front side bi-layer of ITO/SiN this leads to increased Jsc of the device.

Figure 1: Histograms of Jsc distributions for groups of standard HJT cells (blue) and HJT 2.0 cells (orange).

Figure 1 shows the measured Jsc distributions for an experiment with sampling size of a total of 600 cells on standard n-type Cz wafers comparing a single layer ITO and a bi-layer ITO/SiN front electrode. The average Jsc obtained for the ITO single layer standard HJT cells was 38.0mA/cm² while a gain of 0.45mA/cm² or 1.2% relative was measured for the bi-layer ITO/SiN “HJT 2.0” cells.

Simulations using PV-lighthouse’ Wafer Ray Tracer [8] running on the website with the standard libraries results in an already pretty accurate estimation for the measured experimental data, i.e. for the standard cell with the deposited layer thicknesses a Jsc of 38.25mA/cm², for the HJT2.0 bi-layer front side a Jsc of 38.74mA/cm². The difference of the 2 Jscs is just below 0.5mA/cm² and the values of the distribution means are about 0.2mA/cm² slightly higher than measured data. A more accurate simulation should be obtained with PV lighthouse’ SunSolve [9] and the use of the appropriate n, k – data sets for the cells layers that were applied.

EQE measurements reveal the spectral contributions of the Jsc for both cell types. The bi-layer HJT 2.0 cells gain in the IR range from 700-1150nm and in the UV region below 400nm, see figures 2.

Figure 2: Measured and simulated EQEs of a STD HJT cell (above, blue) and improved HJT2.0 cell (below, red). Increased HJT2.0-EQE below 400nm and above 700nm.

When processed properly the Jsc advantage achieved by the optical enhancement of the passivation stack and the front side electrode is not adversely affecting the other cell parameters, i.e. Voc and FF are kept at the same level. This is shown in the corresponding graphs for FF and Voc distributions in figure 3. The distributions of Voc (top) and FF (bottom) exhibit differences of around 1mV for Voc and less than 0.3% absolute for FF, respectively. The distributions are overlapping and the differences of the respective averages are below 0.4% relative while the standard deviation (STD) for the FF is around 0.5% (or 0.4% absolute) and thus considerable less significant than the gain in Jsc.

Figure 3: Histograms of Voc (top) and FF (bottom) for standard HJT (blue) and bi-layer HJT 2.0 (orange).

It is interesting to note that the bi-layer devices tentatively improve in Voc but decrease in FF, for both parameters roughly half of the respective change can be attributed entirely to the increased Jsc of the HJT 2.0 cells. This confirms the optimized “HJT 2.0” process allows for a reduction of conductivity in the front electrode with negligible impact on FF

It might be questioned if the sampling size of 550 to 750 cells per category and the accuracy of IV measurement are sufficient to validate the statistical significance of the observed differences in fitted distribution means for an applied normal distribution. Nevertheless, general considerations with respect to the impact of wafer and TCO conductivities on the cell series resistance confirmed that the bulk which is in high injection when the cell operates supplies sufficient

Figure 4: Histograms of efficiency distributions for cell groups of standard HJT (blue) and HJT2.0 (orange).

conductivity for the majority carriers to facilitate thinner TCOs without adversely impacting on FF [10]. This holds true for a larger range of wafer resistivity since the high quality HJT passivation results in increased life times for higher substrate resistivity and thus increase injection density at MPP which balances the effective conductivity in operation. In consequence an efficiency gain of 0.2% absolute (fitted normal distribution mean) results from the development of the front bi-layer, i.e. from 22.2% for standard single ITO layer HJT cells to 22.4% for the “HJT 2.0” bi-layer cells. The IV measurements were carried out under STC using GridTOUCH contacting [11]. Latest R&D on the ITO/SiN bi-layer resulted in complete preservation of the FF and thus increased the efficiency to 0.3% absolute. Thorough characterization confirmed the same typical low temperature coefficient for power of $-0.25\%/K$ for both HJT and HJT 2.0.

3 PRODUCTION COST CONSIDERATIONS

Indium (In) containing TCOs like ITO or IWO have quite favorable electrical properties however, In was a relatively expensive metal and its market price tended to be volatile not least to speculations with the resource (e.g. listed as ‘strategic metal’) of Chinese market participants. Even though the market and the price of In more or less stabilized since 2016 still In is considered an expensive metal, with an asking price of around 340\$US/kg (September ’19), and price predictions somewhat arbitrary which is often mentioned to deter cell manufacturers to adopt HJT for mass production. The development of a better performing front bi-layer HJT cell that replaces approximately 50% of the total ITO by SiN has a clearly positive impact on production cost since ITO is a main consumable cost contributor for HJT cells. The cost savings stem from reduced consumption and longer tool uptime hence, higher throughput, because for reduced tool maintenance by lesser material deposition, as well as the higher performance of the HJT 2.0 cells.

Figure 5 shows the representation of cost calculations that include the already 2016 anticipated development in the areas of device performance, material cost and tool cost in dependence of time [12].

Figure 5: Graphical representation of a production cost development over time. The CoO reductions are mainly caused by lower consumable costs and CAPEX

reductions by tool cost down. Cost regimes are indicated by arrows for standard HJT (blue) and HJT 2.0 (red)

The transition from the standard HJT device to the HJT 2.0 concepts has impact directly and indirectly on all three factors. A typical 2019 cost calculation scenario is based on a 1GWp production including all cost contributions from infrastructure and building, the appropriate bill of materials, process equipment and time span for depreciation. When applying this full cost calculation to the standard HJT and HJT 2.0 this results in an cost advantage of 0.5ct\$/Wp for the HJT 2.0. Figure 6 depicts the cost projections at module level for both technologies as a function of cell efficiency.

Figure 6: Full cost calculation at module level comparing standard HJT and HJT 2.0 as a function of cell efficiency with an advantage for HJT 2.0 of approximately 0.5ct\$/Wp.

Above shown cost calculations include of course additional tools required for the SiN deposition. The added CAPEX and running costs are off-set by considerable cost saving from the ITO and deposition tool uptime.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The HJT 2.0 concept with the thinner front TCO already shows performance improvements of 0.2-0.3% absolute efficiency. Yet this could go even a step further with a localized ITO under the metallization. This next technology evolution for an improved front side TCO would enable higher currents with higher efficiency if the majority carrier transport is facilitated adequately by the wafer. One could even consider to localize not only the contacts but also the collector, i.e. the a-Si(n) layer thus reducing parasitic absorption in the front even further. Ultimately, the collector/contacts would be moved from the front to the rear of the cell. This IBC-HJT concept is currently developed towards mass production compatibility [13]. Until those latest IBC-HJT cells are ready for the market we consider the HJT 2.0 concept an important step to improve on this one intrinsic performance limitations for HJT cells in the meanwhile, a concept that can be readily transferred into production now.

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